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Chemical Investigations of the Leaves of *Sida rhombifolia* Linn.

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SIDA rhombifolia Linn. has been used in the indigenous system of medicine under the name *Mahabala* for promoting vigour¹ and in urinary and uterine discharges². We have studied the chemical composition of the leaves of this plant. Fifteen free amino acids, six fatty acids and the total sterolic content of the leaves have been isolated and estimated. Antibacterial activity of the mixture of the fatty acids has also been studied.

Experimental

Isolation and estimation of free amino acids : The concentrated 70% ethanolic extract of the defatted leaves was decolourised by refluxing with activated charcoal. The light brown coloured filtrate was then desalted using ion exchange columns³ packed with Amberlite IR 120 (H) and Amberlite IR-45 (OH). The water eluate containing non-ionic constituents gave positive test with Molisch reagent.

Concentrated 5% ammoniacal eluate containing amino acids was spotted on a circular paper chromatogram (Whatman No. 1) and the chromatograms were separately resolved using butanol : acetic acid : water (4 : 1 : 5) and phenol : water (5 : 1). Individual amino acids were identified by R_f values, ninhydrin (0.25% in acetone) colours and co-chromatography with authentic amino acid samples. They were estimated colorimetrically by dissolving each coloured spot in 5.0 ml of 75% ethanol and the optical density measured at 540 nm. The quantities were obtained by interpolation of standard curves. Nine amino acids were identified in the butanol system and six in phenol system. Percentage of individual amino acid in the leaves was lysine 1.7, histidine 1.5, arginine 3.5, asparagine 9.8, glutamine 7.4, alanine 0.98, valine 1.5, phenyl alanine 6.1, leucine 1.7, aspartic acid 0.25, glutamic acid 0.25, glycine 0.31, serine 0.32, threonine 0.38 and tyrosine 0.62.

Isolation and antibacterial activity of fatty acids : The petroleum ether (60-80°) extracted material of the air dried leaves was subjected to alkaline hydrolysis⁴ and the unsaponified material was extracted with solvent ether. The saponified material containing fatty acids was acidified with sulphuric acid and extracted with benzene. The concentrated benzene extracted material was esterified⁴ and extracted with hexane to get the methyl esters of the fatty acids. The glc of the mixed esters showed six different peaks which were identified as those of myristic, palmitic, stearic, oleic and linoleic acids and an unidentified acid.

The antibacterial activity of the mixture of fatty acids was tested using cup-plate method⁵. The mixed fatty acids showed high antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* (inhibition 44 mm) and fairly good activity against *E. coli* (inhibition 26 mm).

Isolation and estimation of sterol : The total phytosterol content in the unsaponified fraction was estimated by colorimetric method described by Zlatkis, Zak and Boyle⁶. The colour of the reaction was measured at 625 nm and compared with that of cholesterol taken as standard. Total phytosterol content in the leaves was found to be 0.052% in terms of cholesterol.

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Gravimetric Determination of Copper(II) Using N-Hydroxy-N-m-tolyl-N'-(2,6-dimethyl)phenylbenzamidinium Hydrochloride

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NUMEROUS complexing reagents such as potassium thiocyanate¹, α -benzoinoxime^{2,3}, salicylaldoxime^{4,5} and rubeanic acid^{6,7} have been suggested for the gravimetric determination of copper(II).

Of these α -benzoinoxime method is the most popular one for routine analysis of copper. However, this method suffers from serious interference due to W(VI), V(V), Fe(III), Zn(II) and ammonium salts. According to Shik⁸, a small amount of cuprous oxide is also precipitated in strongly ammoniacal solution, and the excess of the reagent cannot be removed completely and hence the complex has to be ignited, which is a practical drawback. In the present investigation N-hydroxy-N-*m*-tolyl-N'-(2,6-dimethyl)phenylbenzimidine hydrochloride has been employed as a highly selective precipitant for gravimetric determination of copper(II). The present method in the recommended pH range of 3.0-11.0 eliminates the difficulties stated above. Besides, the reagent possesses a better and favourable gravimetric factor (0.08801) than that of Cu(II)- α -benzoinoximate (0.22002).

Experimental

Apparatus : A systronic pH meter type-322 was used for all pH measurements. A single pan semi-micro balance SAHM-68 (VEB-Analytic GDR) was employed for weighing.

Reagents and chemicals : All the chemicals used were of analytical grade purity.

A stock solution of copper was prepared by dissolving copper metal (B.D.H., AnalaR) in dilute nitric acid and the solution after boiling to expel oxides of nitrogen, was made upto one litre. The copper content of the solution was determined gravimetrically using salicylaldehyde⁹.

The reagent was prepared by condensing N-(2,6-dimethyl)phenylbenzimidoyl chloride and N-*m*-tolylhydroxylamine in equimolar amounts in ether as mentioned earlier⁹. A 1% (w/v) solution of the reagent in ethanol was used for precipitation purposes.

Recommended procedure : An aliquot (25 ml) of the solution containing 10-15 mg of copper(II) ion is diluted to 100 ml in a 400 ml beaker. The pH of the solution is adjusted to 3.0-11.0 using acetic acid, ammonium acetate and ammonia. The solution is warmed to 60-70° and 1% reagent solution (20 ml per 25 mg of copper) is added with stirring till complete precipitation. The precipitate is digested on a boiling water bath for about 20 min with occasional stirring. It is filtered while hot through a previously weighed sintered glass crucible (G-3). The complex is washed with hot water and finally several times with hot 60% ethanol, till the washings give no colour with ferric chloride. The precipitate is dried at 110-120° to constant weight and weighed as $(C_{29}H_{21}N_2O)_3.Cu$ (Found : C, 73.02 ; H, 5.88 ; N, 7.74 ; Cu, 8.82. Calcd. C, 73.18 ; H, 5.81 ; N, 7.76 ; Cu 8.80%).

Properties of copper(II) complex : The reagent solution reacts with cupric ions in slightly acidic to alkaline medium resulting in instantaneous precipitation of a buff coloured, heavy and easily filtrable copper(II) complex. It is insoluble in

water and ethanol, sparingly soluble in acetone, benzene, carbon tetrachloride, chloroform and many common organic solvents. Glacial acetic acid, however, completely decomposes the complex. Excess reagent is easily washed with 60% ethanol. The granular copper complex is highly stable and can be dried at 110-170° without decomposition. The chelate melts at 238° and corresponds to 1 : 2 metal-ligand stoichiometry.

Accuracy and precision : The proposed method gives precise and accurate results. Ten determinations using 12.02 mg of copper each, were performed. The standard deviation and relative standard deviation were found to be ± 0.010 and $\pm 0.09\%$, respectively.

Effect of diverse ions : The estimation of a definite amount of copper was carried out in presence of varying amounts of diverse ions over the pH range 3.0-6.0. The procedure for the determination was the same as described above, except that the pH of the solution was adjusted after the addition of diverse ions. Vanadium(V), iron(II) and iron(III) form coloured complexes with the proposed reagent under the recommended procedure. These ions could be masked with tartaric acid (2 g) and thus the interference due to these ions is eliminated. Cl^- , Br^- , NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} , F^- , Li^+ , Na^+ , K^+ , Rb^+ , Cs^+ (100 mg) ; Hg^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Be^{2+} , Al^{3+} , Cr^{3+} , Bi^{3+} , Pb^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Sb^{3+} , Se^{4+} , Th^{4+} , UO_2^{2+} , Tl^{3+} (50 mg) ; Ti^{4+} , Fe^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , W^{6+} (25 mg) ; V^{5+} , Mo^{6+} (10 mg) do not interfere in the present investigation.

Determination of copper in alloys : An accurately weighed amount of alloy, selected to provide 10-15 mg of copper in 25 ml aliquot of the final solution, was taken in a 250 ml beaker. It was dissolved in minimum quantity of 40% nitric acid. The solution was evaporated to near dryness several times to remove oxides of nitrogen. It was then diluted to 100 ml and the precipitated tin and antimony oxides were filtered off. The residue was washed with hot water followed by a few ml of hot dilute acetic acid and the filtrate was diluted to mark in a 250 ml volumetric flask. A 25 ml aliquot of the solution was pipetted out into a 400 ml beaker and the copper content was determined employing N-hydroxy-N-*m*-tolyl-N'-(2,6-di-methyl)-phenylbenzimidine hydrochloride following the recommended procedure.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF COPPER IN BCS* ALLOYS

BCS sample	Copper found %	Certified value %	Standard deviation
5f Brass	70.72, 70.84, 70.79 Average = 70.78	70.80	± 0.06
6f Gunmetal	87.92, 88.01, 87.93 Average = 87.95	87.90	± 0.07
8c White metal	4.06, 4.06, 4.11 Average = 4.08	4.10	± 0.03

*British chemical standard.

a = in presence of tartaric acid.

It is evident from the results summarised in Table 1 that the amount of copper in the complex material can be determined precisely and accurately.

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